

Risk Assessment

- User Manual -

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1. Introduction

Cyber security risk assessment is a high-level instrument to evaluate the cyber security of a system. It serves as a glue between the management and technical levels helping to analyse the current system state and abstract the results for the further strategic decision making. The main advantage of applying risk assessment is the focus on the concrete needs of the system owner.

In scope of MEDINA, risk assessment serves for the analysis of requirements demanded by a certification scheme and ensuring that fulfilment of these requirements is indeed relevant for the cloud service provider (CSP). Naturally, if a CSP satisfies all requirements it completely complies with the certification scheme and should obtain or maintain the certificate. But, in many real cases some requirements may be insignificant for a CSP (e.g., because they focus on protection of an asset which is not sensitive for this CSP). Such non-conformities should be evaluated, and risk assessment is used for such analysis. The analysis should tell if the detected non-conformities are major ones and the certificate should be revoked, or the deviation is minor and the certificate should be maintained (probably, under some conditions).

Risk assessment functionality is implemented with a Self-Assessment Tool for Risk Analysis (SATRA), which realises a Risk Assessment and Optimisation Framework (RAOF) component. This tool provides the following capabilities:

- Simple and fast EUCS¹-based risk assessment. The risk assessment requires filling in a questionnaire made with EUCS requirements and an asset table. The risk computation itself is performed automatically, taking into account the cloud service level in order to define the most relevant threats to analyse.
- (EUCS-based) Non-conformities assessment. The non-conformities assessment compares risks of full compliance with the risk of reported compliance with EUCS. This analysis of compliance allows to take into account the needs of the CSP.
- Optimisation support. This is an auxiliary functionality which aims to help a CSP to plan his investments in compliance with EUCS and obtain the most optimal system configuration.
- Dynamic and objective risk-based analysis of non-conformities. In contrast to the static risks assessment mentioned above, the information about the compliance with EUCS for dynamic risk assessment is collected by various assessment tools, instead of a human operator. Moreover, this information is provided and analysed in a detailed way, e.g., risk for every asset is computed separately.
- Failure prioritisation support. During the dynamic risk computation, the detected failures are estimated with respect to their contribution to the overall risk picture. These evaluations aim to help the CSP in prioritising the remediation effort.

1.1. User Roles and Permissions

Access to SATRA is managed by Keycloak². The following actions are allowed for the defined roles in the scope of the MEDINA framework.

Role	Allowed Actions
IT Security Governance	Risk Computation (Reporting)
Security Analyst	Risk Computation (Reporting)
Domain Governance	Risk Computation (Reporting)

¹ EUCS (European Cybersecurity Certification Scheme for Cloud Services)

<https://www.enisa.europa.eu/publications/eucs-cloud-service-scheme>

² <https://www.keycloak.org>

Role	Allowed Actions
Product and Service Owner	Create ToE ³ , ToE Info, Questionnaire, Asset Information, Risk Computation (Reporting)
Product (Security) Engineer	Risk Computation (Reporting)
Chief Information Security Office (CISO)	Risk Computation (Reporting)
Customer	None
Auditor	Risk Computation (Reporting)

³ ToE: Target of Evaluation

2. User Manual

2.1. Toolbar

There are only two buttons, named *Select ToE* and *Help*, in the toolbar of the SATRA tool (see Figure 1). The *Select ToE* button leads the user to the initial page of the tool, where he/she can select the ToE (Target of Evaluation) to analyse. The *Help* button opens this manual.

Figure 1. SATRA toolbar

2.2. Select ToE

First, the user should select the ToE to analyse (see Figure 2) by clicking the *Go* button next to the required ToE.

 A screenshot of a web interface titled 'Targets of Evaluation (ToE) available for analysis'. Below the title is a subtitle 'Select a Target of Evaluation for the risk-based analysis.' and a search input field. The main content is a table with columns 'ToE ID', 'ToE Name', and 'Go'. Each row contains a unique ID, a name, a text input field, and a teal 'Go' button.

ToE ID	ToE Name		
0e37d39c-d3ba-4a24-aeaa-380c41cde64c	TestArt2	<input type="text"/>	Go
1bca421e-c708-11ed-afa1-0242ac120002	First ToE	<input type="text"/>	Go
1e67df1a-2127-421a-ba0f-c8731b5e5d3c	TEST STEFANO	<input type="text"/>	Go
2a9c09a7-ebb7-4a97-835c-aa436c1b38b1		<input type="text"/>	Go
2fea17b3-1298-4f8a-af6d-f80e355438d4		<input type="text"/>	Go
34175106-a188-4c7f-9720-53dc7eaa490	First ToE	<input type="text"/>	Go
4b60d24a-c6f4-11ed-afa1-0242ac120002	TEST ToE	<input type="text"/>	Go
5b51bd2-bb00-4512-be37-24819b5d99ab	TestHigh	<input type="text"/>	Go
600e0e76-df6b-11ed-b5ea-0242ac120002	ToE TEST CCE	<input type="text"/>	Go
8cd8c7d0-1446-4cac-ab96-c3f82cd91ab2		<input type="text"/>	Go
90acc728-dfd0-41a7-acd6-0b86500f4568		<input type="text"/>	Go

Figure 2. Selection of ToEs

Next, it is required to set up the Cloud Service Layer of the service, the certification scheme, and the assurance level to comply with (see Figure 3). In the scope of the MEDINA project, only the EUCS certification scheme is supported.

Target of Evaluation Info

Please, provide the cloud service type, select a Certification Scheme and the corresponding Assurance Level (if applicable).

CLOUD SERVICE LAYER
SaaS

CERTIFICATION SCHEME
EUCS

ASSURANCE LEVEL
High

Start Questionnaire

Figure 3. Provide Information about the ToE

After that the user is prompted to indicate whether he/she is interested in conducting static risk assessment or in preparing for the dynamic risk assessment (see Figure 4). The static risk assessment is performed by a user before certification (see section 2.2.1), while the dynamic risk assessment is an integral part of the certificate monitoring process (see section 2.2.3).

The static risk assessment requires two types of information to be provided: information about compliance with the EUCS and main assets. The preparatory step for the dynamic risk assessment prompts only for the sensitivity parameters of the assets (since the information about the current status of the compliance of the service is monitored by various assessment tools without human intervention).

Risk-Based Assessment

Static Risk Assessment The main goal of this "Certification Preparedness Tool" is to provide a simple tool for self-assessing the cyber risk associated to a cloud certification scheme. The tool requires two types of input: information about implemented security measures (based on the selected certification scheme), and information about key assets in the Target of Evaluation. When all inputs are provided the tool estimates the expected annual losses for every individual threat, and also computes the overall estimated loss.

Dynamic Risk Assessment The main goal of the "Certification Continuous Monitoring support tool" is to provide a risk-based non-conformity assessment. The assessment itself is performed during the monitoring phase automatically, but the information about sensitivity of assets should be defined before the monitoring.

Conduct Static Risk Assessment

Prepare for Dynamic Risk Assessment

Figure 4. Select Static or Dynamic Risk Assessment

2.2.1. Static Risk Assessment

During the first step of the static risk assessment (see Figure 5), the user is asked to answer whether the corresponding EUCS requirement is:

- Fully implemented (yes)
- Partly implemented (partial)

- Not implemented (no)
- Not applicable (N/A)

The “partial” option is added for compatibility with the *Catalogue of Controls and Metrics*⁴ (a.k.a. *Catalogue*), as well as for a better representation of the status of compliance. Yet, this option is treated by the risk analysis tool (as it would be treated by the compliance verification process) as “not implemented”. The “Not applicable” option should be used with care, assuming that the CSP has enough evidence to convince the auditor that this requirement is, indeed, not applicable for the CSP.

It is worth noting that the user has the possibility to import his/her answers from the questionnaire of the *Catalogue* (by using the corresponding option). Note, that it is important to set up the same parameters (in particular, the same assurance level used in the *Catalogue*) before starting the risk assessment process. After importing the answers, the user should find the risk assessment questionnaire already prefilled (as much as it was done for the corresponding questions in the *Catalogue*).

The screenshot shows a web-based questionnaire interface. At the top right, there is a button labeled "Select ToE". The main heading is "Questionnaire". Below it, a instruction reads: "Please, answer all questions selecting the most suitable answer from the lists of available answers. Then press Submit." The current page is "Page 1/20. Organisation Of Information Security". The specific section is "Information Security Management System".

Question 1: OIS-01.1H - The CSP shall have an information security management system (ISMS), covering at least the operational units, locations, people and processes for providing the cloud service, with a valid certification of compliance with the requirements of EN ISO/IEC 27001 or with national schemes based on ISO 27001, issued by an accredited CAB covering the cloud service.

Options: Yes, Partial, No, Not Applicable

Question 2: OIS-01.2H - The CSP shall provide documented information of the ISMS applied to the cloud service, including at least: (1) ISO/IEC 27001 requirement 6.1.3 item c) shall be used for the cloud service using the controls in this document for comparison, with the restriction that all controls shall apply. (2) ISO/IEC 27001 requirement 6.1.3 item d) producing a Statement of Applicability referring to the controls in this document for the cloud service

Options: Yes, Partial, No, Not Applicable

Figure 5. Questionnaire

Requirements are organised according to the EUCS structure, i.e., grouped by controls, and controls are grouped by categories. Each of the twenty pages contains questions for a specific category defined by EUCS. Once the user finishes answering questions for a page, he/she should *Go Forward* (see Figure 6). The user can take a break pressing *Save and Leave* to return to the questionnaire later.

⁴ For more detailed information about this component, the interested reader is referred to the MEDINA Deliverable D2.2 <https://zenodo.org/record/7794478>

Contact With Authorities And Interest Groups

OIS-03.1H - The CSP shall maintain regular contacts with relevant authorities in terms of information security and relevant technical groups to stay informed about current threats and vulnerabilities.

Yes.
 Partial
 No
 Not Applicable

Information Security In Project Management

OIS-04.1H - The CSP shall perform a risk assessment according to RM-01 to assess and treat the risks on all projects that may affect the provision of the cloud service, regardless of the nature of the project.

Yes.
 Partial
 No
 Not Applicable

Save and Leave
Go to Cloud Resource
Go Forward

Figure 6. Questionnaire. Bottom

All questions must be answered before the user can move to the second part of the input provisioning process, i.e., the description of the assets. Yet, if all questions are already answered, there is no need to pass through all pages. In this case, it is enough to press the *Go to Cloud Resource* button in Figure 6. The user should press this button at the end of the questionnaire to pass to the next step of the input provisioning process.

At the second step, the user is prompted to provide a list of Cloud Resources and assess their sensitivity (see Figure 7).

CLOUD RESOURCE IDENTIFICATION

ID	Cloud Resource	Cloud Resource Type	Number Of Unit	Confidentiality Level	Integrity Level	Availability Level
A1	<input type="text" value="Insel"/>	IoT Device Provisioning Service	<input type="text" value="1"/>	<input type="text" value="6"/>	<input type="text" value="3"/>	<input type="text" value="3"/>
A2	<input type="text" value="Insel"/>	CI CD Service	<input type="text" value="1"/>	<input type="text" value="6"/>	<input type="text" value="6"/>	<input type="text" value="3"/>
A3	<input type="text" value="Insel"/>	Function	<input type="text" value="1"/>	<input type="text" value="1"/>	<input type="text" value="4"/>	<input type="text" value="3"/>
A4	<input type="text" value="Insert"/>	Database	<input type="text" value="1"/>	<input type="text" value="7"/>	<input type="text" value="3"/>	<input type="text" value="3"/>
A5	<input type="text" value="Insert"/>	Virtual Machine	<input type="text" value="1"/>	<input type="text" value="2"/>	<input type="text" value="3"/>	<input type="text" value="5"/>
A6	<input type="text" value="Insert"/>	Client trust	<input type="text" value="1"/>	<input type="text" value="7"/>	<input type="text" value="3"/>	<input type="text" value="5"/>

+ Create row
Delete row
Submit

Figure 7. Assets collection

Each resource should be one of the 13 supported “Cloud Resource Types”:

- 1 CI CD Service
- 2 Container
- 3 Container Image
- 4 ContainerOrchestration
- 5 ContainerRegistry

- 6 Database
- 7 Function
- 8 IoT Device Provisioning Service
- 9 IoT Messaging Hub
- 10 Local storage
- 11 Network
- 12 Virtual Machine
- 13 VM Image

Once more cloud resource type is obligatory: “Client trust”. It represents how the failure to maintain confidentiality, integrity or availability of the service impacts the future attitude of clients to the cloud service. One resource of this type is added to the list of resources by default. It cannot be removed, and no additional resources of the same type can be added.

In Figure 7, “Number of units” represents the approximate amount of resources of a certain type which belong to the service.

Also, in Figure 7, “Confidentiality, Integrity and Availability levels” indicate the approximate level of losses due to a loss of Confidentiality, Integrity and Availability of the considered resource (e.g., stolen data from a database, or unavailable virtual machine). The rules of thumbs for the levels are as follows:

- 1 Not important at all
- 2 Cause only small inconvenience (e.g., require reboot)
- 3 Systematic malfunctioning with no further consequences
- 4 Some sensitive data is lost
- 5 A portion of sensitive data is lost
- 6 Unnoticed financial abuse
- 7 Failure to function/may stop your business/large amount of data is lost (10,000 affected and more)
- 8 May cause injury/get out of business
- 9 Causing a life loss or a huge amount of sensitive data stolen (10,000,000 affected)
- 10 Catastrophic consequence with several/many lives lost.

New cloud resources can be added to the list, by clicking the *Create row* button, or deleted from the list, by clicking the *Delete row* button (requires indication of the row number).

When the setting of resources is finished, it is required to *Submit* the input. Note, that the tool will ask you to press the *Submit* button twice. After that, the tool computes the risk and analyses the detected non-conformity gap. As a result, the following information is displayed.

First, the radar chart with compliance levels per EUCS category is displayed (see Figure 8).

Figure 8. Compliance radar chart

Second, the overall information about the computed cyber risk for the service is displayed (see Figure 9):

- “Overall Risk” for the service
- “Best” risk level, which can be obtained by implementing all requirements
- Non-conformance gap, which is the difference between the best and overall risk values
- Non-conformance assessment result, which compares the non-conformance gap with a threshold. In case the threshold is exceeded by the non-conformance gap value, the deviation is considered Major (and Minor, otherwise).

Figure 9. Overall risk and non-conformance values

Finally, the risk levels per specific threats are displayed (see Figure 10).

Threat Title	Risk
Third party problems	41.02
Account hijacking (client)	34.14
Meta- interfaces (client)	28.42
CI/CD attacks	0.0
Account hijacking (CSP)	40.19
web-application threat (API, GUI, service vulnerabilities)	0.0
Environment threat (DC)	16.44
Exhaustion of resources (client)	25.97
On-site tampering/penetration	34.75
Data location failure	45.69
Web-based attack	28.28
Unnecessary disclosure to law enforcement	33.09
DoS (client)	18.72
System glitch	42.56
Malicious client employee	24.97
Malicious client	28.31
Exploit insecure IAM (client)	36.04
Lack of support for compositional certification	51.42
Exploit misconfiguration of cloud services (CSP)	34.24
Compromised Communication	24.94
Poor IAM(client)	29.6
Hardware theft/loss (DC)	24.73
Physical threat (DC)	4.69
Exploit misconfiguration of cloud services (client)	38.57
Exploit insecure IAM (CSP)	33.48
Unlawful client	39.35
CSP's employee Negligence and mistakes	40.94
Insider hacker	29.64
Meta- interfaces (CSP)	35.95

Figure 10. Risk per threats

2.2.2. Risk Optimisation

After conducting the static risk assessment, an operator may use the Risk Optimisation mechanism. This mechanism allows an operator to analyse failed requirements and select those of them which may decrease the risk level, taking into account the budget limit for such changes.

In order to use this functionality, an operator should press the *Suggest Optimisation* button at the bottom of the risk results page. The functionality requires two types of input (see Figure 11):

- Budget limit (in euro) available for fixing failed requirements
- Cost of implementing each of the failed requirements

The Budget limit amount must be lower than the sum of all failed requirements, otherwise the selection will be trivial: all failed requirements will be selected. Another extreme is when the Budget limit is lower than the cheapest requirement; the result will be trivial as well: no requirements are to be selected. Note that SATRA counts all requirements marked as *partial*, as failed (since EUCS does not allow partial fulfilment of a requirement).

Risk Mitigation

Providing a budget, the tool will suggest security activities to invest and the optimal expense amount to minimize the overall risk calculated.

Overall Risk:

3.03€

Questions	Cost
PS-01.1B - The CSP shall define security perimeters in the buildings and premises related to the cloud service provided.	1000 <input style="width: 40px;" type="text"/>
OPS-01.1B - The CSP shall define and implement procedures to plan for capacities and resources (personnel and IT resources), which shall include forecasting future capacity requirements in order to identify usage trends and manage system overload.	1000 <input style="width: 40px;" type="text"/>
OPS-18.3B - The CSP shall publish and maintain a publicly and easily accessible online register of vulnerabilities that affect the cloud service and assets provided by the CSP that the CSCs have to install, provide or operate under their own responsibility.	1000 <input style="width: 40px;" type="text"/>
OPS-22.1B - The CSP shall segregate from other CSCs the data stored and processed on shared virtual and physical resources on behalf of a CSC to ensure the confidentiality and integrity of this data.	1000 <input style="width: 40px;" type="text"/>
IAM-01.1B - The CSP shall define role and rights policies and procedures for controlling access to information resources, according to ISP-02 and based on the business and security requirements of the CSP, in which at least the following aspects are covered: (1) Parameters to be considered for making access control decisions; (2) Granting and modifying access rights based on the "least-privilege" principle and on the "need-to-know" principle; (3) Segregation of duties between managing, approving and assigning access rights; (4) Dedicated rules for users with privileged access; (5) Requirements for the approval and documentation of the management of access rights.	9 <input style="width: 40px;" type="text"/>
CKM-01.1B - The CSP shall define and implement policies with technical and organizational safeguards for cryptography and key	

Figure 11. Risk optimisation. Input

Once the input is provided and the procedure is started, the tool will run the optimization procedure and select those requirements whose implementation sum is lower than the target budget and which maximally reduce the risk value. Moreover, the tool computes the target non-conformity gap, assuming that the selected requirements are fulfilled, and reports if the remaining non-conformity is major or minor. Having this information, the CSP may plan its future steps in improving its system and prepare for certification.

2.2.3. Dynamic Risk Assessment

In order to conduct the Dynamic Risk Assessment, the tool needs to be pre-configured. In particular, the information about the sensitivity of the assets should be provided to the system.

After clicking on the button *Prepare for Dynamic Risk Assessment* (see Figure 4), the user will be directed to the page shown in Figure 12, which is very similar to the one for the collection of the information about assets (see Figure 7). Yet, this page is slightly different from its static counterpart.

CLOUD RESOURCE IDENTIFICATION						
ID	Cloud Resource	Cloud Resource Type	Confidentiality Level	Integrity Level	Availability Level	Cloud Resource ID
A1	<input type="text" value="Insert"/>	CI CD Service	1 ▾	1 ▾	1 ▾	
A2	<input type="text" value="Insert"/>	Container	6 ▾	6 ▾	1 ▾	
A3	<input type="text" value="Insert"/>	Function	1 ▾	1 ▾	5 ▾	
A4	<input type="text" value="Insert"/>	Virtual Machine	1 ▾	5 ▾	6 ▾	
A5	<input type="text" value="Insert"/>	ContainerOrchestration	7 ▾	1 ▾	1 ▾	
A6	<input type="text" value="Insert"/>	ContainerRegistry	1 ▾	1 ▾	1 ▾	
A7	<input type="text" value="Insert"/>	Database	5 ▾	5 ▾	1 ▾	
A8	<input type="text" value="Insert"/>	Container Image	6 ▾	1 ▾	1 ▾	
A9	<input type="text" value="Insert"/>	VM Image	6 ▾	6 ▾	4 ▾	
A10	<input type="text" value="Insert"/>	IoT Device Provisioning Service	1 ▾	5 ▾	1 ▾	
A11	<input type="text" value="Insert"/>	IoT Messaging Hub	1 ▾	1 ▾	7 ▾	
A12	<input type="text" value="Insert"/>	Network	5 ▾	3 ▾	1 ▾	
A13	<input type="text" value="Insert"/>	Local storage	3 ▾	2 ▾	2 ▾	
A14	<input type="text" value="Insert"/>	Client trust	3 ▾	5 ▾	8 ▾	
A15	<input type="text" value="Database"/>	CI CD Service	5 ▾	7 ▾	4 ▾	Sdk3-3ddkj-0dkf

Figure 12. Preparation for Dynamic Risk Assessment process. Asset information collection

First, due to the dynamic nature of the cloud, the sensitivity values (i.e., the CIA triad) are assigned to resource types (i.e., these values will be applied to any resource of this type detected by the monitoring tools). Thus, it is required to provide the sensitivity values for all 14 types of Cloud Resources. Yet, if resources of a certain type are not expected to be present in the service under consideration, the values could be left as 1, and will have a negligible effect on the risk computation.

There is also the possibility to add specific resources. For these resources an ID must be provided. During the dynamic risk assessment, if the specific ID is detected, the values specified for this resource will be used (even though this resource may belong to a cloud resource type with other values). Only specific resources can be added or deleted.

The Dynamic risk assessment does not have a human readable output. Its results are used and displayed by other MEDINA components (e.g., *Automated Certificate Life-Cycle Manager*⁵ and *Continuous Certification Evaluation*⁶).

2.2.4. API

Figure 13 shows the APIs implemented by SATRA/RAOF. This API can be used for two purposes:

- 1) Operate the risk and non-conformity assessment process through a custom-built dashboard.
- 2) Use the dynamic risk assessment functionality during the continuous certification monitoring phase by other MEDINA components.

⁵ For more detailed information about this component, the interested reader is referred to the MEDINA Deliverable D4.3 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7927231>

⁶ For more detailed information about this component, the interested reader is referred to the MEDINA Deliverable D4.3 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7927231>

SATRA - Self-Assessment Tool for Risk Analysis ^{0.1}

[Base URL: /api/v1]
/api/v1/swagger.json

Manage interaction with the SATRA engine

registration Register a new practice for that user

- POST** /registration/ToE/ Create a new practice
- GET** /registration/access_resp/{username}/{password} Get the access token from keycloak
- DELETE** /registration/delete_contract/{UUID} Delete a ToE
- PUT** /registration/update_contract/{UUID} Update ToE

practice Interact with the survey, update question/answers and get risk...

- POST** /practice/analysis/{UUID} Send information on a test result
- POST** /practice/answer/{UUID}/{question_id}/{answer_id} Send (eventually, update) an answer for a specific question
- GET** /practice/answer/{UUID}/{type_id} Get all the possible answers by type_id
- GET** /practice/answers/{UUID} Get the question and the answers chosen by the user for the ToE
- POST** /practice/asset_answers/{UUID} Send (eventually, update) an asset answers
- GET** /practice/assets/{UUID} Get all assets type
- GET** /practice/assets_answers/{UUID} Get all assets answer
- DELETE** /practice/assets_answers/{UUID}/{asset_id} Delete a specific asset throughout the name
- GET** /practice/assets_dynamic_answers/{UUID} Get all dynamic assets answer
- GET** /practice/assurance/{UUID} Get all possible assurance levels
- GET** /practice/certification/{UUID} Get all possible certification schemes
- GET** /practice/csp_market/{UUID} Get all possible CSP's markets

POST	/practice/dynamic_evaluated_risk/{UUID}	Dynamic evaluated risk computation
POST	/practice/map/{UUID}	Map an external questionnaire
GET	/practice/non_conformity_gap/{UUID}	Get all possible non conformity gap
GET	/practice/question/{UUID}	Get all the questions
GET	/practice/question/{UUID}/{question_id}	Get one question and its possible answers
GET	/practice/risk/{UUID}	Get the updated risk
GET	/practice/threats/{UUID}	Get the updated threat

Figure 13. SATRA/RAOF APIs

3. Delivery and usage

3.1. Licensing information

This component is offered under Apache 2.0 license. The license files and more detailed information can be found in the MEDINA Public GitLab repository⁷.

3.2. Download

The code of the component is available at the public GitLab repository of the MEDINA project:

<https://git.code.tecnalia.com/medina/public/static-risk-assessment-and-optimization-framework>

3.3. More information

Interested readers can find more information about the *Risk Assessment and Optimisation Framework* at this link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7927217> D2.8 Risk-based techniques and tools for Cloud Security Certification – v3.

The MEDINA web site (<https://medina-project.eu/>) also includes several deliverables and blog posts related to the RAOF.

⁷ <https://git.code.tecnalia.com/medina/public/static-risk-assessment-and-optimization-framework>